

MECHANISMS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE AMONG EDUCATORS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS BASED ON A PERSON-ORIENTED APPROACH

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the mechanisms of formation and development of professional competence among teachers of preschool educational organizations based on a person-oriented approach.*

Keywords: *competence, development, mechanism, educator's professionogram.*

The future and development of independent Uzbekistan was determined by the development of science and education. Therefore, since the first years of Uzbekistan's independence, the issues of education, science and vocational training have been considered as a priority direction of our state's policy.

In particular, to strengthen the foundations of our independence, to take a place in Uzbekistan among the developed countries in the development of society, to rationally implement educational activities. informing the young generation about the achievements of modern science, culture, technology and technology, educating a person with high moral character, and enriching their spiritual world is considered a necessity.

After all, the development of our country is good for the growing of young generation who will be spiritually mature. It is in the hands of intelligent, responsible, intellectually developed young people who have a strong will, a strong faith, are independent and proud, and can work freely. For this, the worldview, upbringing, and manners of each educator are considered to be of particular importance in his behavior. The main tool of the behavior culture of an educator is language. There is a proverb in our people: "A child is a beggar of sweet words", so the educator should be very careful and attentive to the language in his dealings. A sweet-spoken, courteous teacher is the most respected and attentive. The process of education is especially important for children of preschool age. Preacher Koshifi, when talking to a child, only use good words, don't use bad words, because it will negatively affect the child's ability to swim and speak. promotes. Alisher Navoi mentions the opinion that the first thing in the skill of the person dealing is the sweetness of the language, "Sweet words are honey for the soul." A wise man looked at the team and said: - I have something to say, I will sell it for a thousand soums. he said. The participants of the conversation were surprised and asked "what is the matter?" Then a wise man, this saying: - "Think and act"! means, he said, from this idea of a wise man, it should be understood that a person who thinks and acts should have an image in his behavior (control his head, face and behavior in terms of manners). Leaving no room for rude and obscene words, treating the child with rudeness that hurts the child's appetite, harms the teacher's honor and reputation. Pedagogical scientist Sukhomlinsky described the power of communication skills and its hidden secrets in the work "Sacrifice to Children": "... A teacher with a high sense of culture immediately understands the

unpleasant mood of the kindergarten. First of all, this can be seen from his eyes, ... He finds a way to make it known that he feels the anxiety in the child's heart. Then he can find the child alone and inquire.

It is necessary to understand the child's condition, to sympathize with him, to help him.

Often, sympathy and compassion are the closest help to a child's heart. Carelessness and indifference make the child's tongue tremble!

It is important for an educator to be fair while forming a culture of treatment. So what is justice? What is meant by justice? So, justice is a measure that separates faith, faith, and good intentions from injustice. Justice is an important criterion for evaluating human behavior. Such a requirement is the initial stage of living with a group of children. Creator-pedagogue A.S. Makarenko said that "it is impossible to start training the team without a sincere, transparent, convincing, intense and strict demand. Such requirements to start the team on the path to a common goal:

- the demand is positive and does not affect the child's behavior;
- the requirement should be clear and understandable;
- to know the result of the request;
- the request is given with an open face, in a sincere tone: a request, advice, invitation in good faith;
- the requirement should correspond to the age and level of education of the children;
- cutting demands, biting, not thanking, etc.

Another form of pedagogical influence of the teacher is to start the children's lama on the path of independence. In this case, it is important to have transparency and trust between educators and students in the team, self-management, and adherence to traditions and laws.

The educator uses various educational methods to bond the children's team. In general, the theoretical and practical foundations of team organization and its educational impact have been studied and researched by thinkers and scientists.

The next task of the educator is to master the theoretical knowledge of the organization, education and cohesiveness of the children's team, relying on best practices to teach the students in the educational process comradeship, mutual cooperation, solidarity, self-education and consists in mastering the skill of educating public qualities such as management. They are:

- teaching children in a group and creating mutual relations among them.
- students' integration into the team in all aspects of their daily activities.
- teaching to put the collective interest above personal interest.
- if there is mutual kindness, kindness and generosity, friendly cooperation in the team, it becomes a great educational force.

When organizing groups of students, the teacher is required to skillfully use various methods and tools:

1. During the period of adaptation of the members of the educational team to the new conditions, it is necessary to be able to trust, respect, politely, set the requirements correctly, and at the same time, to acquire the skills of understanding and listening to the child;
2. Selection of the core of the leading force in the team of educators;
3. Assign tasks according to the strength and abilities of each team member;
4. Creating and following the initial budding of new traditions and rules in the team.

It is required to define the perspective of the team in accordance with the demand of the time.

A child of preschool age is active and active, he tries to get to know the world around him as quickly as possible, he tries to find his place in the team. A child's mobility, interest in knowing everything, hobby and desire to do independent work are characteristic features of a preschool child. These characteristics are primarily reflected in the child's games. The child's attitude to the outside world is expressed in games. Home is also necessary for the physical development of the child.

Children reflect the life around them in their games. Preschool children develop a lot of clear ideas by sensing and perceiving the objects around them. Children of this age think very clearly. They like to imitate adults in their games. For example, boys often imitate soldiers and make it their game to win over the enemy, while girls often play with dolls and in their games they do everything related to keeping a household: cleaning the house, cooking, putting their children to sleep, dressing them, feeding them, taking them to the movies, etc. In the games of preschool children, sometimes their interest in professions is also shown.

Sometimes it can be seen that a child puts a chair on the ground and drives it as a car, trying to implement the rules of driving a car. A child neatly puts his toys in a corner, puts his dolls in their place, loads or unloads his car, bakes "desserts" from sand, makes "ice cream", makes a house. Child labor is not limited to play. He collects everything he can get his hands on, except the toys that were bought for him. For example, he collects candy wrappers, matches, leather, cigarette boxes, tree leaves, nails, wire, spools of thread and uses them in his play and uses them in his construction work. When children play in groups, they want to be the leader, to play only human, "good" roles and, of course, to win.

Our thinkers put forward the opinion that it is possible to determine children's interest in work and learn their talent through games. A.S. Makarenko says: "The way a child is at play, when he grows up, he will be at work in many ways." According to the great pedagogue, a good game is like a good work, the first characteristic of every good game is hard work and use of thought.

The game makes the child happy, and good work gives the same joy. Through the game, the culture of behavior is formed in children, the wealth of speech increases. The greater the responsibility at work, the greater the responsibility at play. This is especially true for my child's games, which are mostly played individually and as a team.

It should also be said that educators and parents should not say "don't give to anyone" when they organize and hold children's games, because we are not only raising a member of the community, but a selfish person need

Children's play and children's work are inextricably linked, and play is an activity organically linked to children's age. In this regard, Maxim Gorky said: "A child wants entertaining games up to the age of three, his desire is biologically legitimate. He wants to play, he plays games like everyone else, and he knows and recognizes the world around him better and more easily through games than anyone else," he wrote.

In the game, children's inclinations and interests, their relationship to the life around them are clearly visible. So, the game is one of the most important means of developing a child. That's why the game, skillfully organized by skilled teachers and parents, helps to raise a child mentally, physically and morally, and thus prepares him for life and practical activities.

In the process of interactive games, the child can correctly express his independent opinion, learns to listen to others, in other words, through interactive games positive qualities that are the basis for every child in the future are formed. Interactive

For effective games, you should pay attention to the following rules:

1. To what extent do children know the rules and content of the game before the lesson to determine their understanding.
2. Children's age characteristics and their relationship to each other to consider.
3. Taking into account the abilities and psychological characteristics of each child.
4. Use of materials that are interesting to children during the game.
5. Finding styles that attract attention and attention.
6. Proper distribution of mercy to children.
7. Knowing how the game can be used.
8. To have an idea about the main stages of the game and its results forecasting.

From a pedagogical point of view, a properly organized game is moral and voluntary of a child while forming its characteristics, to gain knowledge in it, the secrets of the surrounding world is interested in opening. That's why the game in preschool educational institutions technologies should be widely used.

The concept of game technology is a component of pedagogical technology.

The technology of the game differs from the traditional game method in its specific purpose, the logical sequence of the processes to be implemented and their interaction depends on the guarantee of achieving predetermined results.

CONCLUSION In conclusion, it should be noted that education is pedagogical targeted use of technology and interactive methods, preschool children optimization of intellectual abilities, forms of education, independence of children it leads to the growth of activity and the achievement of educational efficiency.

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